

An Overview on μ_N Strongly Nowhere Dense Sets

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Abstract: In this article we have introduced some new types of sets such as μ_N strongly dense, μ_N strongly nowhere dense, μ_N strongly first category sets, μ_N strongly nowhere residual sets and their attributes are explained briefly. Also by making use of these we have retrieved μ_N strongly Baire space and its properties are to be described.

Key words: μ_N strongly dense, μ_N strongly nowhere dense, μ_N strongly first category sets, μ_N strongly nowhere residual sets

1. Introduction

Zadeh's concept of fuzziness has a huge impact on all fields of mathematics. C.L.Chang[3] later combined the ideas of fuzziness with topological spaces, laying the groundwork for the theory of fuzzy topological spaces. K.T.Attanasov[1] discovered intuitionistic fuzzy sets, and with his friend Stoeva[2], he expanded his research to reveal a generalisation to intuitionistic L-fuzzy sets. F.Smarandache[7] directed his attention to the degree of indeterminacy and proposed the neutrosophic sets. Following that, A.A.Salama and Albowi[13] discovered the neutrosophic topological spaces using neutrosophic sets. We[12] created Generalized topological spaces via neutrosophic sets using all of the works as inspiration and named it as TS. In μ_N TS the concept of Baire space was put forth by us and here we extended our research ideas into the strong natures of μ_N Baire space.

2. Necessities

Definition 2.1. [14] Let X be a non-empty fixed set. A Neutrosophic set [NS for short] A is an object having the form $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ where $\mu_A(x)$, $\sigma_A(x)$ and $\gamma_A(x)$ which represents the degree of membership function, the degree of indeterminacy and the degree of non-membership function respectively of each element $x \in X$ to the set A .

Remark 2.1. [14] Every intuitionistic fuzzy set A is a non empty set in X is obviously on Neutrosophic sets having the form $A = \{ \langle \mu_A(x), 1 - (\mu_A(x) + \sigma_A(x)), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$. Since our main purpose is to construct the tools for developing Neutrosophic Set and Neutrosophic topology, we must introduce the neutrosophic sets 0_N and 1_N in X as follows: 0_N may be defined as follows

$$(0_1) 0_N = \{ \langle x, 0, 0, 1 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

1_N may be defined as follows

$$(1_1) 1_N = \{ \langle x, 1, 0, 0 \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Definition 2.2. [14] Let $A = \{ \langle \mu_A, \sigma_A, \gamma_A \rangle \}$ be a NS on X , then the complement of the set A [$C(A)$ for short] may be defined as three kinds of complements :

$$(C_1) C(A) = A = \{ \langle x, 1 - \mu_A(x), 1 - \sigma_A(x), 1 - \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$$

Definition 2.3. [14] Let X be a non-empty set and neutrosophic sets A and B in the form $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ and $B = \{ \langle x, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \gamma_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$. Then we may consider two possibilities for definitions for subsets ($A \subseteq B$).

$A \subseteq B$ may be defined as :

$$(A \subseteq B) \iff \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \leq \sigma_B(x), \gamma_A(x) \geq \gamma_B(x) \forall x \in X$$

Proposition 2.1. [14] For any neutrosophic set A , the following conditions holds:

$$0_N \subseteq A, 0_N \subseteq 0_N$$

$$A \subseteq 1_N, 1_N \subseteq 1_N$$

Definition 2.4. [14] Let X be a non empty set and $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \gamma_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ $B = \{ \langle x, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \gamma_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ are NSs. Then $A \cap B$ may be defined as :

$$(I_1) A \cap B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_B(x), \gamma_A(x) \vee \gamma_B(x) \rangle$$

$A \cup B$ may be defined as :

$$(I_1) A \cup B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \vee \sigma_B(x), \gamma_A(x) \wedge \gamma_B(x) \rangle$$

Definition 2.5. [12] A μ_N topology is a non - empty set X is a family of neutrosophic subsets in X satisfying the following axioms:

$$(\mu_{N_1}) 0_N \in \mu_N$$

(μ_{N_2}) union of any number of μ_N open set is μ_N open.

Remark 2.2. [12] The elements of μ_N are μ_N -open sets and their complement is called μ_N closed sets.

Definition 2.6. [12] The μ_N - Closure of A is the intersection of all μ_N closed sets containing A .

Definition 2.7. [12] The μ_N - Interior of A is the union of all μ_N open sets contained in A .

Definition 2.8. [13] A neutrosophic set A in NTS is called neutrosophic dense if there exists no neutrosophic closed sets B in (X, T) such that $A \subset B \subset 1_N$.

Definition 2.9. [13] The μ_N Topological spaces is said to be μ_N Baire's Space if $\mu_N \text{Int}(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} G_i) = 0_N$ where G_i 's are μ_N nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) .

Proposition 2.2. [13] Let (X, μ_N) be a μ_N TS. Then the following are equivalent.

1. (X, μ_N) is μ_N Baire's Space.
2. $\mu_N \text{Int}(A) = 0_N$, for all μ_N first category set in (X, μ_N) .
3. $\mu_N \text{Cl}(A) = 1_N$, for every μ_N Residual set in (X, μ_N) .

3. μ_N Strongly Nowhere Dense sets:

Definition 3.1. Let (X, μ_N) be a μ_N Topological Space. A neutrosophic sets ζ defined on (X, μ_N) is called μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) if $\zeta \wedge \bar{\zeta}$ is a μ_N nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) . That is, ζ is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) if $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\zeta \cap \bar{\zeta})) = 0_N$ in (X, μ_N) .

Proposition 3.1. *If ζ is a μ_N nowhere dense set in a μ_N Topological Space (X, μ_N) , then ζ is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N)*

Proof. Let ζ be a μ_N nowhere dense set in a μ_N Topological Space in (X, μ_N) , then $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\zeta)) = 0_N$ in (X, μ_N) . Since $\zeta \wedge \bar{\zeta} \subseteq \zeta$ in (X, μ_N) . We obtain that $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\zeta \cap \bar{\zeta})) \subseteq \mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\zeta))$ and hence $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\zeta \cap \bar{\zeta})) \subseteq 0_N$. That is, $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\zeta \cap \bar{\zeta})) = 0_N$. Hence ζ is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) . \square

Proposition 3.2. *If $\bar{\zeta}$ is a μ_N nowhere dense set in a μ_N Topological Space in (X, μ_N) , then ζ is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) .*

Proof. Suppose that $\bar{\zeta}$ is a μ_N nowhere dense set in a μ_N Topological Space in (X, μ_N) , then $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\bar{\zeta})) = 0_N$ in (X, μ_N) . Since $\zeta \cap \bar{\zeta} \subseteq \bar{\zeta}$, $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\zeta \cap \bar{\zeta})) \subseteq \mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\bar{\zeta}))$ and hence $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\zeta \cap \bar{\zeta})) \subseteq 0_N$ that implies us $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\zeta \cap \bar{\zeta})) = 0_N$. Hence ζ is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) . \square

Proposition 3.3. *If $\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mu_N \text{Int}\bar{\zeta}) = 1_N$, for a neutrosophic set ζ defined on (X, μ_N) , then ζ is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) .*

Proof. Suppose that $\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mu_N \text{Int}\bar{\zeta}) = 1_N$ in (X, μ_N) . Then we deduce that $\overline{\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mu_N \text{Int}\bar{\zeta})} = 0_N$ which implies us $\overline{\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}\zeta)} = 0_N$. We obtain $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}\zeta) = 0_N$. Thus, ζ is a μ_N nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) . By using proposition 3.2, ζ is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) . \square

Proposition 3.4. *If ζ is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) , then $\bar{\zeta}$ is also a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set.*

Proof. Let ζ be a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) which entails us that $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\zeta \cap \bar{\zeta})) = 0_N$ in (X, μ_N) . Now $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\bar{\zeta} \cap \bar{\bar{\zeta}})) = \mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\bar{\zeta} \cap \zeta)) = 0_N$. This implies us $\bar{\zeta}$ is also a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) . \square

Proposition 3.5. *If ζ is a μ_N nowhere dense set in μ_N Topological space then $\bar{\zeta}$ is μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) .*

Proof. Let ζ be a μ_N nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) . Now by using Proposition 3.2 we get ζ is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) and by proposition 3.4 we obtain that $\bar{\zeta}$ is μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) . \square

Proposition 3.6. *If ζ is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) , then $\mu_N \text{Cl}(\zeta \cup \bar{\zeta}) = 1_N$.*

Proof. Let ζ be a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) then we obtain that $\mu_N Cl(\zeta \cup \bar{\zeta}) = 0_N \Rightarrow \mu_N Cl(\overline{\mu_N Int(\zeta \cap \bar{\zeta})}) = 1_N \Rightarrow \mu_N Cl(\mu_N Int(\overline{\zeta \cap \bar{\zeta}})) = 1_N$. But $\mu_N Cl(\mu_N Int(\bar{\zeta} \cup \zeta)) \subseteq \mu_N Cl(\bar{\zeta} \cup \zeta) \Rightarrow 1_N \subseteq \mu_N Cl(\bar{\zeta} \cup \zeta)$. Hence we get $\mu_N Cl(\zeta \cup \bar{\zeta}) = 1_N$. \square

Proposition 3.7. *If $\mu_N Int \mathbf{P}$ is a μ_N dense set, for a neutrosophic set \mathbf{P} defined on a μ_N TS (X, μ_N) then \mathbf{P} is μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) .*

Proof. Suppose that $\mu_N Int \mathbf{P}$ is a μ_N dense set in (X, μ_N) , then $\mu_N Cl(\mu_N Int \mathbf{P}) = 1_N$ in (X, μ_N) . Then $\overline{\mu_N Cl(\mu_N Int \mathbf{P})} = 0_N$. This implies us $\mu_N Int(\mu_N Cl \bar{\mathbf{P}}) = 0_N$ in (X, μ_N) . Since $\mathbf{P} \cap \bar{\mathbf{P}} \subseteq \bar{\mathbf{P}}$ we deduce that $\mu_N Int(\mu_N Cl(\mathbf{P} \cap \bar{\mathbf{P}})) \subseteq \mu_N Int(\mu_N Cl \bar{\mathbf{P}})$ and hence $\mu_N Int(\mu_N Cl(\mathbf{P} \cap \bar{\mathbf{P}})) \subseteq 0_N$. That is $\mu_N Int(\mu_N Cl(\mathbf{P} \cap \bar{\mathbf{P}})) = 0_N$ which implies us that \mathbf{P} is μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) . \square

Proposition 3.8. *If \mathbf{P} is a neutrosophic set defined on (X, μ_N) such that $\mu_N Int(\mu_N Fr(\mathbf{P})) = 0_N$ in a μ_N Topological space then \mathbf{P} is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) .*

Proof. Let \mathbf{P} be a neutrosophic set defined on (X, μ_N) such that $\mu_N Int(\mu_N Fr(\mathbf{P})) = 0_N$. Since $\mu_N Fr(\mathbf{P}) = \mu_N Cl(\mathbf{P}) \cap \mu_N Cl(\bar{\mathbf{P}})$ and we know that $\mu_N Cl(\mathbf{P} \cap \bar{\mathbf{P}}) \subseteq \mu_N Cl(\mathbf{P}) \cap \mu_N Cl(\bar{\mathbf{P}})$. Now $\mu_N Cl(\mathbf{P} \cap \bar{\mathbf{P}}) \subseteq \mu_N Fr(\mathbf{P}) \Rightarrow \mu_N Int(\mu_N Cl(\mathbf{P} \cap \bar{\mathbf{P}})) \subseteq \mu_N Int(\mu_N Fr(\mathbf{P})) = 0_N$. Hence we get $\mu_N Int(\mu_N Cl(\mathbf{P} \cap \bar{\mathbf{P}})) = 0_N$ that implies us \mathbf{P} is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) . \square

Definition 3.2. A neutrosophic set in a μ_N Topological space is called μ_N simply open set in (X, μ_N) if $\mu_N Fr(\mathbf{P})$ is μ_N nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) . In otherwords, \mathbf{P} is μ_N simply open set iff $\mu_N Int(\mu_N Cl(\mu_N Fr \mathbf{P})) = 0_N$ in (X, μ_N) .

Proposition 3.9. *If \mathbf{P} is a μ_N simply open set in a μ_N Topological space (X, μ_N) , then \mathbf{P} is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) .*

Proof. Let \mathbf{P} be a simply open set in (X, μ_N) . Then $\mu_N Int(\mu_N Cl(\mu_N Fr \mathbf{P})) = 0_N$ in (X, μ_N) . But $\mu_N Int(\mu_N Fr \mathbf{P}) \subseteq \mu_N Int(\mu_N Cl(\mu_N Fr \mathbf{P}))$. From this we obtain that $\mu_N Int(\mu_N Fr \mathbf{P}) = 0_N$ in (X, μ_N) . Then by using proposition 3.8 we obtain that \mathbf{P} is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) . \square

Remark 3.1. *The converse of the above proposition need not be true. This can be illustrated in the example given below.*

Example 3.1. *Let (X, μ_N) be a μ_N TS where $X = \{a, b\}$ and we define neutrosophic sets $\delta_1 = \{< 0.6, 0.4, 0.8 > < 0.8, 0.6, 0.9 >\}$, $\delta_2 = \{< 0.6, 0.3, 0.8 > < 0.9, 0.2, 0.7 >\}$, $\delta_3 = \{< 0.5, 0.4, 0.9 > < 0.7, 0.8, 0.9 >\}$, $\delta_4 = \{< 0.4, 0.6, 0.9 > < 0.6, 0.8, 0.9 >\}$, $\delta_5 = \{< 0.3, 0.7, 0.9 > < 0.5, 0.9, 0.9 >\}$ and $\mu_N = \{0_N, \delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3, \delta_4\}$ be a μ_N TS here the μ_N simply open sets are $\{0_N, \delta_2, \delta_5, 1_N\}$ and the μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets are $\{0_N, \delta_2, \delta_3, \delta_5, 1_N\}$. Here δ_5 is μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) but not μ_N simply open set in (X, μ_N) .*

Proposition 3.10. *If \mathbf{P} is a μ_N closed set with $\mu_N Int(\mathbf{P}) = 0_N$ in a μ_N TS (X, μ_N) , then \mathbf{P} is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) .*

Proof. Let \mathbf{P} be a μ_N closed set with $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mathbf{P}) = 0_N$ in (X, μ_N) . Then $\mu_N \text{Int} \mu_N \text{Cl}(\mu_N \text{Cl} \mathbf{P} \cap \mu_N \text{Cl} \overline{\mathbf{P}}) = \mu_N \text{Int} \mu_N \text{Cl}(\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mu_N \text{Int} \mathbf{P}}) = \mu_N \text{Int} \mu_N \text{Cl}(\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{0_N}) = \mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl} \mathbf{P}) = \mu_N \text{Int} \mathbf{P} = 0_N$. Hence, we get \mathbf{P} is a μ_N simply open set in (X, μ_N) . By proposition 3.9 deduce that \mathbf{P} is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) . \square

Proposition 3.11. *If \mathbf{P} is a μ_N open set and μ_N dense set in a μ_N Topological space (X, μ_N) , then \mathbf{P} is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) .*

Proof. Let \mathbf{P} be a μ_N open and μ_N dense set in (X, μ_N) . Then $\overline{\mathbf{P}}$ is a μ_N closed set with $\mu_N \text{Int} \overline{\mathbf{P}} = \overline{\mu_N \text{Cl} \mathbf{P}} = 0_N$ in (X, μ_N) . Then by using proposition 3.10 we retrieve that $\overline{\mathbf{P}}$ is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) and by using the proposition 3.4 we obtain that $\overline{\mathbf{P}}$ is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) which implies us that \mathbf{P} is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) . \square

Proposition 3.12. *Every subset of μ_N strongly nowhere dense set is μ_N strongly nowhere dense set.*

Proof. Let \mathbf{P} be a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set, then $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}})) = 0_N$. If $\zeta \subseteq \mathbf{P}$ we have $\zeta \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}} \subseteq \overline{\mathbf{P}} \Rightarrow \mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\zeta \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}})) \subseteq \mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}})) = 0_N$. Therefore ζ is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set. Hence, subset of μ_N strongly nowhere dense set is μ_N strongly nowhere dense set. \square

Proposition 3.13. *A neutrosophic set is μ_N strongly nowhere dense set if and only $\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mu_N \text{Int}(\overline{\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}}})) = 1_N$.*

Proof. Suppose \mathbf{P} is μ_N strongly nowhere dense then $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}})) = 0_N$. Now, $\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mu_N \text{Int}(\overline{\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}}})) = \mu_N \text{Cl}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\overline{\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}}})) = \overline{\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}}))} = 1_N$. Conversely we assume that $\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mu_N \text{Int}(\overline{\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}}})) = 1_N$. On considering, $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}})) = \overline{\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}}))} = \overline{\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mu_N \text{Int}(\overline{\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}}}))} = \mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}})) = 0_N$. Hence it is μ_N strongly nowhere dense set. \square

Proposition 3.14. *If \mathbf{P} is μ_N strongly nowhere dense set then $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}}) = 0_N$.*

Proof. Suppose \mathbf{P} is μ_N strongly nowhere dense then $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}})) = 0_N$. Now, $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}}) \subseteq \mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Cl}(\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}})) = 0_N$. Hence, $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mathbf{P} \cap \overline{\mathbf{P}}) = 0_N$. \square

4. μ_N strongly first category sets in μ_N TS:

Definition 4.1. A neutrosophic set is said to be μ_N stongly first category set in μ_N TS if $\delta = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \delta_i$ where δ_i 's are μ_N stongly nowhere dense sets. The left out sets are called as μ_N stongly second category sets. The complement of μ_N stongly first category sets are called μ_N stongly residual sets.

Example 4.1. *Let (X, μ_N) be a μ_N TS where $X = \{a, b\}$ and we define neutrosophic sets $L_1 = \{< 0.6, 0.4, 0.8 > < 0.8, 0.6, 0.9 >\}$, $L_2 = \{< 0.6, 0.3, 0.8 > < 0.9, 0.2, 0.7 >\}$, $L_3 = \{< 0.5, 0.4, 0.9 > < 0.7, 0.8, 0.9 >\}$, $L_4 = \{< 0.4, 0.6, 0.9 > < 0.6, 0.8, 0.9 >\}$, $L_5 = \{< 0.3, 0.7, 0.9 > < 0.5, 0.9, 0.9 >\}$ and $\mu_N = \{0_N, L_1, L_2, L_3, L_4\}$ be a μ_N TS. Here μ_N stongly first category set is $L_2 = \{< 0.6, 0.3, 0.8 > < 0.9, 0.2, 0.7 >\}$. The μ_N stongly second category sets are $0_N, 1_N, L_1, L_3, L_4$ and the μ_N stongly residual set is $\overline{L_2}$.*

Proposition 4.1. *If \mathbf{P} is a μ_N first category set then \mathbf{P} is μ_N strongly first category set.*

Proof. Let \mathbf{P} be a μ_N first category set in a μ_N TS. Then $\mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$ where \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N nowhere dense sets in μ_N TS. By making use of the fact "Every μ_N nowhere dense set is μ_N strongly nowhere dense set" we deduce that \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets and hence $\mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$ where \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets. Therefore, \mathbf{P} is μ_N strongly first category set. \square

Remark 4.1. *Every μ_N strongly first category sets need not be μ_N first category set. It is exemplified below.*

Example 4.2. *Let $X = \{a\}$ and $\mu_N = \{0_N, A, C, E\}$ be a μ_N TS where $0_N = \{< 0, 1, 1 >\}$, $A = \{< 0.7, 0.8, 0.9 >\}$, $B = \{< 0.3, 0.4, 0.6 >\}$, $C = \{< 0.9, 0.7, 0.6 >\}$, $1_N = \{< 1, 0, 0 >\}$. Here the μ_N first category set is $0_N = \{< 0, 1, 1 >\}$ and the μ_N strongly first category set is $C = \{< 0.9, 0.7, 0.6 >\}$. From this clearly we deduce that the μ_N strongly first category sets need not be μ_N first category set.*

Proposition 4.2. *If $\mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$ where \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N closed sets with $\mu_N \text{Int} \mathbf{P} = 0_N$ then \mathbf{P} is a μ_N strongly first category set.*

Proof. Suppose $\mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$ where \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N closed sets with $\mu_N \text{Int} \mathbf{P} = 0_N$ in a μ_N TS (X, μ_N) . Then by the fact, "If \mathbf{P} is μ_N closed in μ_N TS with $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mathbf{P}_i) = 0_N$ then \mathbf{P} is μ_N strongly nowhere dense set". By making use of this theorem we deduce that \mathbf{P} is μ_N closed in μ_N TS with $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mathbf{P}_i) = 0_N$. Thus, \mathbf{P} is μ_N strongly nowhere dense set and then we have $\mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$ where \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets. Thereupon \mathbf{P} is a μ_N strongly first category set. \square

Theorem 4.1. *If $\mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$ where $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Fr}(\mathbf{P}_i)) = 0_N$ then \mathbf{P} is μ_N strongly first category set.*

Proof. Assume that $\mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$ where $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Fr}(\mathbf{P}_i)) = 0_N$. By theorem, "If $\mu_N \text{Int}(\mu_N \text{Fr}(\mathbf{P})) = 0_N$ for a μ_N open set in μ_N TS then \mathbf{P} is μ_N strongly nowhere dense set." By making use of this we obtain that \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets. Therefore, $\mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$ where \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets and hence \mathbf{P} is μ_N strongly first category set. \square

Theorem 4.2. *If $\mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$ where \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N open sets in μ_N TS then \mathbf{P} is μ_N strongly first category set.*

Proof. Given that $\mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$ where \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N open sets in μ_N TS and also μ_N dense set in μ_N TS. By theorem, "If \mathbf{P} is a μ_N open set in μ_N TS and \mathbf{P} is also μ_N dense set in (X, μ_N) , then \mathbf{P} is a μ_N strongly nowhere dense set in (X, μ_N) ." By making use of this theorem we obtain that \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets and $\mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$, where \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets. Thereupon we get \mathbf{P} is μ_N strongly first category set. \square

Theorem 4.3. *Every subset of μ_N strongly first category set is μ_N strongly first category set.*

Proof. Let \mathbf{P} be a μ_N strongly first category set. Then $\mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$ where \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets. Suppose $\zeta \subseteq \mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$. From this we deduce that $\zeta \subseteq \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$ which implies us that $\zeta \subseteq \mathbf{P}$ for some μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets. By using proposition 3.14 we obtain that ζ is μ_N strongly first category set. \square

Remark 4.2. *Superset of μ_N strongly first category set need not be μ_N strongly first category set. This can be explained in the below example.*

Example 4.3. Let $\mu_N = \{0_N, \tau_a, \tau_b\}$ where $0_N = \{\langle 0, 1, 1 \rangle\}$, $\tau_a = \{\langle 0.1, 0.4, 0.6 \rangle\}$, $\tau_b = \{\langle 0.2, 0.3, 0.5 \rangle\}$, $\tau_c = \{\langle 0.6, 0.6, 0.1 \rangle\}$, $\tau_d = \{\langle 0.5, 0.7, 0.2 \rangle\}$. Here, $\tau_c = \{\langle 0.6, 0.6, 0.1 \rangle\}$ is μ_N strongly first category set but $\bar{\tau}_b \supseteq \tau_c = \{\langle 0.6, 0.6, 0.1 \rangle\}$ but $\bar{\tau}_b = \{\langle 0.5, 0.7, 0.2 \rangle\}$ is not μ_N strongly first category set.

5. μ_N Strongly Baire Space:

Definition 5.1. A μ_N TS is called μ_N strongly Baire space if $\mu_N Cl(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i) = 1_N$ where \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets.

Example 5.1. Let $X = \{a\}$ and $\mu_N = \{0_N, A, C, E\}$ be a μ_N TS where $0_N = \{\langle 0, 1, 1 \rangle\}$, $A = \{\langle 0.7, 0.8, 0.9 \rangle\}$, $B = \{\langle 0.3, 0.4, 0.6 \rangle\}$, $C = \{\langle 0.9, 0.7, 0.6 \rangle\}$, $1_N = \{\langle 1, 0, 0 \rangle\}$. Here the μ_N first category set is $0_N = \{\langle 0, 1, 1 \rangle\}$ and the μ_N strongly first category sets are $C = \{\langle 0.9, 0.7, 0.6 \rangle\}$ and $1_N = \{\langle 1, 0, 0 \rangle\}$. $\mu_N Cl(1_N) = 1_N$. Hence (X, μ_N) is a μ_N strongly Baire space.

Theorem 5.1. Let (X, μ_N) be a μ_N TS. Then the following statements are parallel in nature.

1. (X, μ_N) is a μ_N strongly Baire space.
2. $\mu_N Cl(\mathbf{P}) = 1_N$, for every μ_N strongly first category set.
3. $\mu_N Int(\mathbf{P}) = 0_N$, for every μ_N residual sets.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii). Let \mathbf{P} be a μ_N strongly first category set in (X, μ_N) . Then $\mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$ where \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets. Since (X, μ_N) is a μ_N strong Baire space we get $\mu_N Cl(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i) = 1_N$. Hence, $\mu_N Cl(\mathbf{P}) = 1_N$.

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii). Let \mathbf{P} be a μ_N strongly residual set in (X, μ_N) . Then we retrieve that $\bar{\mathbf{P}}$ is a μ_N strongly first category set in (X, μ_N) . From (ii) we obtain that $\mu_N Cl(\bar{\mathbf{P}}) = 1_N \Rightarrow \overline{\mu_N Int(\bar{\mathbf{P}})} = 1_N$. Hence, $\mu_N Int(\mathbf{P}) = 0_N$.

(iii) \Rightarrow (i). Let \mathbf{P} be a μ_N strongly first category set in (X, μ_N) . Then $\mathbf{P} = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i$ where \mathbf{P}_i 's are a μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets. We have if \mathbf{P} is a μ_N strongly first category set then $\bar{\mathbf{P}}$ is a μ_N strongly residual set in (X, μ_N) . Now by making use of (iii) we obtain that $\mu_N Int(\bar{\mathbf{P}}) = 0_N$ which gives us that $\overline{\mu_N Cl(\bar{\mathbf{P}})} = 0_N$. Therefore we get $\mu_N Cl(\mathbf{P}_i) = 1_N$ and hence $\mu_N Cl(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{P}_i) = 1_N$ where \mathbf{P}_i 's are a μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets. Hence, (X, μ_N) is a μ_N strongly Baire space. \square

Theorem 5.2. If $\{\mathbf{P}_i\}, i = 1$ to ∞ is μ_N open set and μ_N dense set in μ_N TS then (X, μ_N) is a μ_N strongly Baire space.

Proof. We know that, "If ζ is μ_N open set and μ_N dense then ζ is μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets". By making use of this fact we obtain that \mathbf{P}_i 's are μ_N strongly nowhere dense sets in (X, μ_N) . Let $\xi = \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \xi_i$ then ξ_i 's are μ_N strongly first category sets. Now, $\mu_N Cl(\xi_i) = \mu_N Cl(\cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \xi_i) \supseteq \cup_{i=1}^{\infty} \mu_N Cl(\xi_i) = 1_N$. Hence, (X, μ_N) is a μ_N strongly Baire space. \square

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